

Construction of Wind-Solar Hybrid Charge Controller

Win Zaw Myo Htet*, Myo Lwin**, Lwan Htet Nay Aung***

Abstract

Wind-solar hybrid controller is constructed by using an Arduino Uno. These controllers used high ampere dc relays, which use switching between dump load and battery. The 4-lines LCD is used to display the battery voltage, charging current and operation mode of the controller circuit. LM 385 dual comparator Op-Amp IC is used to sense the charging current and battery voltage. The A/D module of an Arduino Uno is used to convert the LM385 outputs into digital form which are used as the reference values in the program. When the battery voltage reaches about 14.5 volt, the output is switched to a Dump Load. If battery volt is equal to or lower than 12.1 volt, the system starts charging the battery.

Keywords: hybrid controller, A/D module

Introduction

For the past few years, many researches have been developing small power systems that can be used in locations where there is no electricity or in locations that suffer constant power outages. Different from a generator which is too heavy, too loud and requires fuel, so researchers are focusing on small hybrid systems.

Hybrid Renewable Energy Systems (HERS) are becoming popular for providing electricity in remote areas. Due to advances in renewable energy technologies, Green House Gas (GHG) emission, Chlorofluorocarbons (CFC) emission and air pollution can be reduced. A hybrid energy or hybrid power consists of two or more renewable energy sources which used together to provide increasing system efficiency as well as greater balance in energy supply. Solar power from a photovoltaic system and wind power from a wind turbine will be combined to generate more output power of electricity. Solar panel or photovoltaic (PV) cells absorb sun beam by radiation and give electrical energy output. Solar panels are the medium to convert solar power into electrical power.

A wind turbine obtains its power input by converting the force of the wind into torque (turning force) acting on the rotor blades. Unlike a generator, a hybrid system uses clean energy, runs quietly and can be easily transported when compared to standard systems. In Hybrid Renewable Energy Systems (HERS), charge controller is important one for the system. Charge controller is the main component for energy management for the whole system. An energy management system is necessary to keep the energy balance of this hybrid system.

The people from urban region where there is no electricity are using solar cell but most of people are not using charge controller. They do not know to use charge controller and the advantages of using charge controller. Charge controller has basic function is that it control the source which is to be active or inactive. It simultaneously charge battery and also gives power to the load. The controller has over-charge protection, short-circuit protection, pole confusion protection and automatic dump load function. It is also the function is that it should vary the power as per the load demand. When power is not generating it should extract power from battery and give it to the load.

* Assistant Lecturer, Department of Physics, Bago University

** Dr., Professor, Department of Physics, University of Yangon

*** Lecturer, Department of Physics, Bago University

In this research, an Arduino Uno is used to control the whole system. LM358 dual operational amplifier IC is used to sense voltage and current of battery and optocoupler and MOSFET are used to control the charging rate not to damage the battery as PWM method. The whole operation is shown as block diagram in Figure 1.

Figure. 1 Block Diagram of Hybrid Charge Controller

The Arduino Uno

The Arduino Uno is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega328 microcontroller. It has 14 digital input/output pins (of which 6 can be used as PWM outputs), 6 analog inputs, a 16 MHz ceramic resonator, a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header, and a reset button. It contains everything needed to support the microcontroller; simply connect it to a computer with a USB cable or power it with an AC-to-DC adapter or battery to get started. The Uno differs from all preceding boards in that it does not use the FTDI USB-to-serial driver chip. Instead, it features the Atmega16U2 (Atmega8U2 up to version R2) programmed as a USB-to-serial converter.

"Uno" means one in Italian and is named to mark the upcoming release of Arduino 1.0. The Uno and version 1.0 will be the reference versions of Arduino, moving forward. The Uno is the latest in a series of USB Arduino boards, and the reference model for the Arduino platform; for a comparison with previous versions, see the index of Arduino boards. Photo of Arduino Uno is shown in Figure 2.

Summary

Microcontroller	ATmega328
Operating Voltage	5V
Input Voltage (recommended)	7-12V
Input Voltage (limits)	6-20V
Digital I/O Pins	14 (of which 6 provide PWM output)
Analog Input Pins	6

DC Current per I/O Pin	40 mA
DC Current for 3.3V Pin	50 mA
Flash Memory	32 KB (ATmega328) of which 0.5 KB used by bootloader
SRAM	2 KB (ATmega328)
EEPROM	1 KB (ATmega328)
Clock Speed	16 MHz

Figure. 2 Photo of the Arduino Uno

LM358 Dual Operational Amplifier

LM358 Dual Operational Amplifier consists of two op-amps internally and frequency compensated operational amplifiers which were designed specifically to operate from a single power supply over a wide range of voltage. Operation from split power supplies is also possible and the low power supply current drain is independent of the magnitude of the power supply voltage. Application areas include transducer amplifier, DC gain blocks and all the conventional OP amp circuits which now can be easily implemented in single power supply system. In this research LM358 is used as voltage and current sensing of the battery to send information to PIC. Photograph and Pin diagram of LM358 IC are shown in Figure 3 and 4.

Figure. 3 Photograph of LM358 IC

Figure. 4 Pin Diagram of LM358 IC

Operation of the Whole System

The operation of the system is controlled by an Arduino Uno. Arduino senses the battery voltage by using its Analog to Digital module. The input voltage comes from LM 358 dual comparator op-amp IC. LM 358 controls the voltage that is PIC microcontroller unit can accept.

When the Arduino detects the battery voltage is about 14.5V, it cutoff the power from wind and solar panel and activate the dump load. The red LED will ON and the words “CHARGING FULL” will be displayed on LCD that there is fully charged. PIC controls the switching transistor and Double-Pole, Double- throw (DPDT) relay. That can handle 25A maximum. So, the panel’s power can’t sink to the battery. The 3A diodes are used not to go back battery voltage to the power source.

In full-charged condition, the battery must be about 14.5V. The battery will fall down to 12V in a few minutes. Then the battery will stable 12V if it have not load. When the PIC detects battery voltage is under 12.1 V, Arduino charges the battery from power source by switch on the C1383 transistors and DPDT relay. This condition is charging and the green LED will light up and the words “CHARGING” will be displayed on LCD. When the switch of the controller is off, the relay is normally open and all the current from wind and solar will flow to

the damp load. Figure 5 and 6 show the whole circuit diagram and photograph of wind-solar hybrid charge controller circuit with Arduino Uno.

Figure. 5 The Whole Circuit Diagram of Wind-Solar Hybrid Charge Controller Circuit with Arduino Uno

Figure. 6 Photograph of Wind-Solar Hybrid Charge Controller Circuit with Arduino Uno

Figure. 7 Photograph of Hybrid Charge Controller while Charging with Arduino Uno

Figure. 8 Photograph of Hybrid Charge Controller while Charging Full with Arduino Uno

Conclusion

The wind and solar hybrid charge controller circuit acts as a control circuit to regulate the process of wind turbine and solar panel battery charging process. These circuits can be constructed from discrete electronic components. The circuit operation is based on matching the wind and solar cell terminal load voltage to the appropriate number of battery cell units to be charged depending on the total power output of hybrid power source. Two methods of charging with PWM and without PWM have been tested. Charging with PWM is more convenient than charging without PWM in order to save the battery life but charging rate is

slower. Arduino Uno is easier to assemble and easier to change program. The hybrid voltage regulator is designed for 12V system employing panels of up to total current 10A. If we increase the Dump Load's watt and MOSFET transistor, it can handle more power of wind and solar hybrid system with this circuit.

Future Plan

Higher power solar panel and wind turbine will be used and hybrid charge controller will be modified to be able to resist high power. The wind turbine will be designed and constructed. Solar panel will be added to the system. Wind speed and light intensity will be measured in research area. The whole system will be portable and efficiency will be analyzed in selective research area.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Rector Dr Aye Aye Tun, Bago University for her encouragement to do this work. I would like to thank to Professor Dr Khin Mar Ohn, Head of Department of Physics, Bago University, for her kind permission to carry out this work. I wish to show my sincere thanks to Professor Dr Khin Htoo, Department of Physics, Bago University, for encouraging me to carry out this work. I am thankful for the valuable guidance and support provided by Dr Myo Lwin, Professor, Department of Physics, Yangon University. And my thanks also goes to U Thant Shwe, Lecturer, Department of Physics, Bago University and U Nay Win Tun, Lecturer, Department of Physics, Taunggyi University for their help in programming and suggestion for this work. Without their guidance and feedback, the work could not have been a success.

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